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EXPLORING THE ELEMENTS OF CASTEISM IN THE NOVEL OF DR. S. L. BHYRAPPA: DAATU (CROSSING OVER)

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Abstract: *Daatu* written in the early 70's by Dr. S. L. Bhyrappa, is the magnificent work. The fiction is set on the backdrop of much trending caste system deeply rooted in India. It goes on exploring the social, political and economic conditions with an inter-caste marriage between a Brahmin girl and a Gowda boy as a central subject of the story. The novel has won the Sahitya Akademi Award in 1975. The story is set in Thirumalapura. The village has been named after the temple of Lord Tirumala. At the very beginning of the novel, readers get acquainted with the fact that the villagers have been arguing on the matter that whether the temple of Lord Tirumala belongs to Shiva Pantheon or Vaishnavas. The story revolves around two main families- Venkataramanayya, who comes from Brahmin family and the other is a flag bearer Gowda family, headed by Tirumale Gowda who studied all major Scriptures which were earlier reserved only for the Brahmins.

Key words: *India, diversity, Unity, inter-caste marriage, Hindu civilization, casteism etc.*

Introduction: India is well known for its diverse identity in language, religion, culture and literature. It is one of the countries where the highest numbers of languages are being spoken. As per the survey done by Census of India of 2001, India has 122 major languages and 1599 other languages. In the 8th Schedule of Indian Constitution, 22 languages have been mentioned as scheduled languages and given the status and official encouragement. Apart from this in the year 2004, the Government of India granted the Classical status to Kannad, Malyalam, Odia, Sanskrit, Tamil and Telugu languages which have a rich heritage and independent nature. It can be considered that the India writes in many languages and speaks in many more voices. Instead of this diverse identity, communication, in this soil has never broken down. Literature being one of the best means of expression and communication, playing a vital role in keeping alive the cultural, lingual, and traditional heritage of the land from thousands of years. India is being recognized due to its literary grandeur. Ancient Indian literature existed even before the invention of writing skill. It was being transmitted from generation to generation through oral tradition. The composition of epics such as '*Ramayan*' and '*Mahabharat*' led by the oral storytelling tradition. The earliest form of speech in oral in India can be found in the oldest preserved treatises such as- the '*Rig Veda*', the '*Upanishadas*' etc. The earlier works, before the invention of writing skill, were composed to be recite, that they can be easily transmitted orally for the upcoming generations. As per the Indian Literature is concerned, it is one of the most ancient literatures which has set a role model to the rest of the world. Apart from literature, India is well known for its cultural and religious diversity. India has set a role model before the world that how it is possible to live in harmony irrespective of religious diversity. As most of the Indian population practices Hinduism, there are many other religions like Islam, Christianity, Sikhism, Buddhism, Jainism etc. have their own history and significance in Indian context.

Though India gives the message of "*Unity in Diversity*", the nation itself is split on the basis of caste, creed etc. Hinduism is the largest religion in India. The Caste system is found to be very rigid in Hindu religion. Caste system is divided Hindus into four main stratum, popularly known as Varnas- *Brahmins, Kshatriyas, Vaishyas and Shudras*. In ancient India, caste system was an institution. The result of excessive practice of the caste system was social hierarchy, which led to the conflict between upper and lower castes. Brahmins were the most dominant

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class in the history of Hindu civilization. The period of nearly 400 years between 1000 B.C and 600 B.C., when Brahmins won the status of upper caste and strengthened their position at the top in Indian caste system. With human beings, the caste system was also extended to the Gods, animals, etc. For example:

"Agni and Brihaspati are the Brahmanas;
Indra, Varuna, Soma, Rudra, Parjanya and Yama are the Kshatriyas,
8 Vasus, 11 Rudras, 12 Adityas, Visadevas and Maruts are Vaishyas
And Pusan is Sudra".

The monopoly of power of Brahmins divided the Hindu society into many fragments in ancient India. The caste system which exists in Indian society is thought to be the outcome of the changes during the collapse of the Mughal Empire and the rise of the British Raj. British colonizers built their government by creating rigid caste system as a central mechanism of their administration. That's why it is said that the Britishers believed in the system i.e. '*Divide and Rule*'. They executed the caste system into their administration by granting the jobs and senior appointments only to the Christians and people belonging to certain castes especially upper. Though the rigid caste system has been criticized by many Indian social reformers like Mahatma Basavanna, Mahatma Jyotirao Phule, Dr. B. R. Ambedkar etc. we find chunks of the same in Indian society especially in Hinduism.

Dr. S.L. Bhyrappa is the best-selling Kannada novelist, and is perhaps the most translated novelist in India today. Bhyrappa's works do not fit into any specific genre of contemporary Kannada literature such as *Navodaya*, *Navya*, *Bandaya* or *Dalita* partly because of the range of topics he writes about. Bhyrappa's latest novel *Avarana*, created a record by going for twenty-two reprints in just two years. Two of his novels have been translated into all fourteen official languages of India (*Daatu* (1972) and *Tantu* (1993)), while several others have been translated into many regional languages especially Marathi and Hindi. Starting with *Bheemakaya*, first published in 1958, Bhyrappa has authored twenty four novels in his career spanning more than five decades. To mention *Belaku Mooditu* (1959), *Dharmashree* (1961), *Vamshavriksha* (1965), *Jalapaata* (1967), *Naayi Neralu* (1968), *Tabbaliyu Neenade Magane* (1968), *Gruhabhanga* (1970), and *Grahana* (1972). *Vamshavriksha* has received the *Kannada Sahitya Academy Award* in 1966 and *Daatu* (Crossing Over) received both *Kannada Sahitya Academy and Kendra Sahitya Academy* award in 1975.

Daatu written in the early 70's by S. L. Bhyrappa is the magnificent work. The fiction is set on the backdrop of one of the burning issues of Indian society i.e. deeply rooted caste system. The fiction goes on exploring the social, political and economic condition with an inter-caste marriage between a Brahmin girl and a Gowda boy as the central subject of the story. The story is set in Thirumalapura. The village has been named after the temple of Lord Tirumala. At the very beginning of the novel readers get acquainted with the fact that the villagers have been arguing on the matter that whether the present temple of Lord Tirumala belongs to Shiva Pantheon or Vaishnavas. The story revolves around two main families- Venkataramanayya, who belongs to Brahmin family and the other is from a flag bearer Gowda family, headed by Tirumale Gowda who studied all major Scriptures which were reserved only for the Brahmins long ago.

The twist comes into the story when Satyabhama, a History graduate and daughter of Venkataramanayya decide to marry Srinivas, the grandson of Tirumale Gowda. This leads to the conflict between two families, two castes and quarrel among the villagers over the matter that which caste is better. Both family members get involved in this matter. Everyone tries their hand to stop the marriage. But with the use of power and influence in the village, Melgiri Gowda (father of Srinivas) succeeds in stopping the marriage. As the story progresses further, the author

tries to unravel the major reasons of the rigid caste system and misconceptions regarding the same among the villagers. The character of Satyabhama becomes the mouthpiece of the author in the process of unleashing the puzzle of caste system. Satya from her early childhood is a studious girl who persuaded her father to teach her some *Upanishad* like '*Ishaavaasya*'. Afterwards in her college days she went on studying some popular English books on women's status in Vedic age and on Indian culture. Then being a curious student of History, she starts studying the Indian history deeply along with the history of other countries. With the help of detailed study of Indian civilization, society and the system of caste-distinction, Satya get to know that the caste system was not so rigid and discriminative in early Vedic period as it is now. Her studious nature leads her to be rational.

We come across some myths and misconceptions spread among the people about the caste system, especially about the superiority of Brahmins. In the novel, while contemplating on the Varna structure the explanation by History teacher occurs into the mind of Srinivas that the Vedas say the four castes came out the four parts of the Lord. This is one example of the misconceptions strongly infused in the minds of common mass. The author gives an instance of another myth rumored how the Brahmin girl may turn into Goddess Maramma. The concept of the Goddess Maramma is a fine blending of elements like- myth, folklore and legend. According to the belief among the non-Brahmin mass, a Brahmin woman burns herself along with her husband and children when she comes to know that her husband being an untouchable, had deceived her by lying that he belonged to Brahmin caste. From then the Brahmin woman is worshipped as Goddess Maramma in India, especially in Southern region. People believe that the goddess protects the village from the diseases like plague, cholera. This goddess is worshipped mostly by the people from lower strata. The fair and festivals also celebrated in the name of Goddess Maramma. Animal sacrifice is one of the rituals performed during the festival. According to the story of Goddess, sung while the sacrifice of the bull, the untouchable youth lied, dared to learn Vedas and married Brahmin girl and out of the sexual intercourses he begot children. The bull, which to be sacrificed is the husband who deceived the Brahmin girl and the ships represent her children. These are some systematic techniques how the people belonging to upper strata tried to marginalize the people from lower strata and kept them deprived from the sources of knowledge from thousands of years. It was declared during Vedic period that Brahmin and knowledge were inseparable. A formula- *Brahmin is equal to knowledge and knowledge is equal to Brahmin was fixed*. The monopoly of power was completely vested with the monopoly of knowledge. This monopoly of knowledge and power has created irreparable crack in Indian society. Mr. Kasinath K. Kavlekar in his book '*Non-Brahmin Movement in South India 1873-1849*' written in reference to the caste system in India that caste in ancient India was an institution. The literature written between 1000 B.C. and 600 B.C. represents the most vital period of institution of Aryan society in India, which has its deep impact on the Hindu world. During this period the Brahmins won the highest status in the society. When we look into the later Vedic age we find that Brahmins became dominant by covering a wide range of area. As Brahmin gained the religious leadership they had an advantage of influencing psychology of the entire society. As a result the whole Vedic literature is more or less ritual literature composed by Brahmins. "*Taittiriya Brahmana declares that Brahman is all gods and Brahmins therefore belong to the group of god*" ('*Non-Brahmin Movement in South India 1873-1849*', p.no. 3). This is how they went on claiming their position to that of Gods.

Conclusion: The fiction itself is the lighthouse to understand the minor details of the caste system which has been in practice form the ages. Every minor and major character plays vital role in unleashing the *casteism* throughout the story. Now in this 21st century everyone got an access to the education. The credit of this revolution of course goes to the social reformers and

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makers of The Constitution of India. Dr. B. R. Ambedkar said that the education is the only weapon which can bring the change in our society and lead us towards the progress. Satya, who is being the best byproduct of education, decides to help Mohandas by writing a book on his request for the benefits of Dalits. The book helps to create awareness among Dalits/Untouchables to understand the injustice done to them. Likewise education only will help the society to come out of all these conflicts- who is Brahmin?, who is Untouchable? Whose caste is superior? and whose caste is inferior?

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